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**LITERARY AND NONLITERARY FORMS OF SPEECH IN ENGLISH
AND UZBEK**

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ANNOTATION

This article deals with the analysis of literary and nonliterary forms of speech in English and Uzbek in Linguacultural studies.

KEY WORDS: - language, literary forms of speech, Uzbek, English, Non-literary forms of speech.

Language, as a vehicle of expression, encompasses an array of stylistic and communicative forms. In English and Uzbek, this diversity is particularly pronounced, with distinct literary and non-literary forms of speech shaping both creative and practical communication.

Literary Forms of Speech:

In both English and Uzbek, literary speech ensconces a rich tradition of artistic expression. English literature boasts a vast repertoire of poetic forms, prose, drama, and creative writing. These forms are characterized by their use of inventive language, stylistic devices, and profound thematic exploration. English literary speech, whether in the form of a Shakespearean sonnet or a modern novel, seeks to evoke emotion, ponder the human condition, and present thought-provoking exploration of life's myriad facets.

Similarly, in Uzbek, literary speech showcases profound poetic traditions, enriched by famed poets through the ages. Classic and contemporary poetry, as well as novels and short stories, serve as vehicles of cultural preservation and artistic conveyance, drawing on rich imagery, traditional references, and poetic rhythms to engage and captivate readers.

Non-literary Forms of Speech:

In contrast, non-literary speech in both languages occupies a realm of everyday communication, technical writing, official discourse, and information dissemination. In

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English, non-literary speech encompasses an array of pragmatic forms including academic essays, scientific reports, technical manuals, official announcements, and various modes of correspondence. This domain emphasizes clarity, precision, and professionalism, tailoring language to suit specific communicative needs.

In Uzbek, non-literary speech mirrors this practicality, spanning official, technical, and everyday discourse. From instructional manuals to official documents, and colloquial exchanges, non-literary speech takes on a variety of register, ensuring that information is conveyed accurately while meeting specific communicative goals.

In both English and Uzbek, there are distinct forms of speech used in varied contexts, including literary and non-literary expressions. Let's briefly explore these forms in each language:

English:

1. Literary Forms of Speech:

- In English literature, there are various forms of speech, including poetry, prose, drama, and creative writing. These forms often utilize a rich vocabulary, figurative language, and stylistic devices to convey nuanced meanings and evoke emotions.

2. Non-literary Forms of Speech:

- Non-literary forms of speech in English encompass everyday communication, business language, scientific writing, technical documents, and other professional or informal contexts. These forms prioritize clarity, directness, and specificity in conveying information. They may include genres such as essays, articles, reports, emails, and various types of non-fiction writing.

Uzbek:

1. Literary Forms of Speech:

- In Uzbek literature, there are also various literary forms, including classic poetry, contemporary poetry, novels, short stories, and plays. Literary speech in Uzbek often employs rich imagery, traditional cultural references, and poetic structures to convey emotion and meaning.

2. Non-literary Forms of Speech:

- Non-literary forms of speech in Uzbek encompass everyday spoken communication, official and governmental language, technical writing, and various forms of professional discourse. These forms prioritize clarity and precision in conveying information, often reflecting cultural norms and specific regional dialects.

In both languages, the distinction between literary and non-literary forms of speech lies in the context of usage, the level of formality, and the intended audience.

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Literary speech emphasizes creativity, artistic expression, and aesthetic appeal, while non-literary speech prioritizes clarity, direct communication, and the exchange of practical information.

These distinctions influence the vocabulary, syntax, and stylistic devices used in each form, reflecting the diverse richness of language and communication within both English and Uzbek linguistic traditions.

Certainly, I'd be happy to provide examples of literary and non-literary forms of speech in both English and Uzbek.

Literary Forms of Speech:

English:

- Literary: A Shakespearean sonnet by William Shakespeare, a poem by Emily Dickinson, or a novel by Jane Austen, such as "Pride and Prejudice," exemplify classic literary forms characterized by poetic language, rich imagery, and thematic depth.

- Non-literary: A scientific research article, a business report, or a user manual represent practical non-literary forms in English, structured to convey specific information and to facilitate clear understanding without poetic embellishment.

Uzbek:

- Literary: Works by prominent Uzbek poets such as Alisher Navoi and Hamid Alimjan, or renowned Uzbek novels like "Sunnat" by Erkin Vohidov, showcase literary speech rich in traditional cultural references and poetic expression.

- Non-literary: Official decrees, technical manuals for industrial equipment, or formal business correspondence serve as examples of non-literary forms in Uzbek, prioritizing precision and clarity in conveying specific information and instructions.

Examples:

Literary Speech - English:

Opening lines from "To Kill a Mockingbird" by Harper Lee:

"Maycomb was a tired, old town, even in 1932 when I first knew it."

Non-literary Speech - English:

An excerpt from a user manual:

"To reset the device, press and hold the power button for 10 seconds until the status LED begins to flash. Release the power button to complete the reset process."

Literary Speech - Uzbek:

A verse from an Alisher Navoi poem:

"O'zim so'z mam yana zamonun, yana umrim

Ko'zim ko'rmadi osmonun beshi, ko'nglida ot jangrim."

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Non-literary Speech - Uzbek:

A section from an official decree:

"Xodimlarimizga e'lon qilinadigan bayram kunlari yo'qotiladi. Shunga ko'ra, zarur izohlarni va ma'lumotlarni qulaylik bilan e'lon qiling."

These samples illustrate the distinguishing characteristics of literary versus non-literary forms of speech in both English and Uzbek, offering an insight into their versatile expression and function across various contexts.

Conclusion: The juxtaposition of literary and non-literary forms of speech in both English and Uzbek highlights the multi-dimensionality of language. While literary speech cherishes creativity, emotional depth, and cultural resonance, non-literary speech leans toward efficient information exchange, practicality, and professional communication. The coexistence of these forms encapsulates and celebrates the diverse nuances and expressive potential of both languages, reflecting a rich tapestry of linguistic legacy that continues to evolve. In both languages, the interplay of literary and non-literary speech underlines the adaptability and encompassing nature of human expression, providing a vibrant spectrum that resonates with the myriad complexities of the human experience.

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